

BLUE ACTION

Blue-Action

Arctic Impact on weather and climate

Scope

Blue-Action aims to:

- improve our understanding of the impact of a changing Arctic on Northern Hemisphere weather and climate;
- improve the safety & wellbeing of people in the Arctic and across the Northern Hemisphere;
- reduce the risks associated with Arctic operations and resource exploitation; and,
- support evidence-based decision-making by policymakers worldwide.

Blue-Action aims to work with:

- Researchers and projects focussing on Arctic and northern hemisphere observing, climate modelling, forecasting, and climate services.
- Governments and policymakers in need of weather and climate information for evidence-based decision-making.
- NGOs, public sector bodies, and community organisations interested in extreme weather events, climate services, forecasting, and climate change.
- Businesses or industries who rely on seasonal to decadal climate predictions, risk estimates of extreme weather, and understanding climate events, or who would like to work with Blue-Action to co-develop climate services and tools.

What we expect to achieve

Blue-Action co-designs a series of case studies with organisations and industries that rely on accurate weather and climate forecasting, to apply new modelling techniques to cutting-edge climate services. In addition to the maritime sectors we address specifically fisheries, tourism, health and arctic industries.

Project details

Budget EUR 8 103 125 (EUR 7 500 000 EU Contribution)

Duration 2016-12-01 to 2021-02-28

Call BG-10-2016

Type of Action RIA

Website www.blue-action.eu

Social media @BG10Blueaction

Blue-Action

Project Partners (affiliation)	Country code	Project Partners (affiliation)	Country code
Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut (Coordinator)	DK	Marine Research Institute	IS
Arctic Centre of the University of Lapland	FI	Marine Scotland Science	UK
Almada City Council	PT	National Center for Atmospheric Research (*)	US
Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici	IT	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center	NO

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	FR	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research	NL
Department of Atmospheric Sciences at Yonsei University /Climate Theory Lab (*)	KR	Netherlands eScience Center	NL
DNV GL Norway	NO	Natural Environment Research Council, National Oceanography Centre	UK
Danish Pelagic Producers Organisation	DK	Pelagic Freezer-trawler Association	NL
Technical University of Denmark	DK	Rukakeskus Oy	FI
Foresight Intelligence GbR	DE	Scottish Association for Marine Science	UK
GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel	DE	SAMS Research Services Ltd	UK
Faroe Marine Research Institute	FO	Universitaet Hamburg	DE
Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (*)	CN	University of Bergen	NO
A.M. Obukhov Institute of Atmospheric Physics of Russian Academy of Sciences (*)	RU	Uni Research	NO
Institute For Advanced Sustainability Studies e.V.	DE	University of Southampton	UK
Fundacio Institut		University of	US

Catala de Ciencies del Clima (participation terminated in 2017)	Washington - Applied Physics Laboratory (*)	
Institute of World Economy and International Relations (*)	The University of Reading	UK
Konsortium für die Deutsche Meeresforschung	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (*)	US
MEOPAR Incorporated (*)	World Ocean Council	UK
MERCATOR OCEAN	Fundacion Privada Instituto de Salud Global Barcelona	ES
Max Planck Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Wissenschaften e.V.	Climate-KIC ApS	DK

Event participant(s) information, areas of interest, contact information

Name of participant and contact information (e-mail)	Main area of interest and expertise	Participant's photo (optional)
Steffen M. Olsen smo@dmi.dk (Coordinator)	Arctic impact on weather and climate.	

